

FROM THE SECOND COMING TO SEPTEMBER 1, 1939 AND LONDON RAIN

Éva Székely
University of Oradea

Abstract: *The present paper is an intertextual study of the representation of evil in three modernist poems: W.B. Yeats's emblematic poem written after the end of World War I, and W.H. Auden's and Louis MacNeice's poems written at the outbreak of World War II.*

Key words: *modernist, poetry, evil, World War II, representations*

The following paper is an intertextual study of the representation of evil in three modernist poems: W.B. Yeats's *The Second Coming*, W. H. Auden's *September 1 1939*, and *Louis MacNeice's "London Rain"*. When speaking of evil, I refer to what Calder Todd calls "the narrow concept of evil," i.e., moral evil only: the most despicable deeds, characters, events, etc. ("The Concept of Evil". *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*)

As a preamble to the discussion of the poems, I will take a look at one of the most influential writings of Friedrich Nietzsche: *The Genealogy of Morals*. The reason for which the discussion of Nietzsche is mandatory here is that I am convinced that this work had a profound influence on Yeats's view on good and evil in general and on his poem: *The Second Coming* in particular. Therefore, after the summing up of the main ideas in the Prologue and the first essay of *On the Genealogy of Morality*, I shall proceed to a discussion of the impact of Nietzsche's views on Yeats's poem, and then to the effect of Yeats's "The Second Coming" on W.H. Auden's "September 1 1939" and Louis MacNeice's "London Rain".

Friedrich Nietzsche: *On the Genealogy of Morals. A Political Tract*

Nietzsche's *On the Genealogy of Morals. A Political Tract* (1887) is a highly influential work in which the author questions key contemporary Judeo-Christian moral premises. The study is structured into a "Prologue"

and three essays. It is probably the most systematic study written by Nietzsche. In my paper, I shall refer to the ideas developed in the "Prologue" and the first essay entitled: "'Good and Evil,' 'Good and Bad.'"

The fundamental premise of the *Genealogy* is that there are no moral universals, that morality is deeply rooted in the power dynamics between humans, and that changes in history can trace these changes in morals. In the first essay, "'Good and Evil,' 'Good and Bad'" Nietzsche presents us a narrative according to which humanity has progressed from a **pre-moral stage to a moral stage**. He states that in the beginning, there was no morality in the conventional sense of the word. People did things without any moral judgement about them. Their actions were either beneficial or detrimental. Things were not deemed "good" or "evil". In other words, whatever the strong did, how they acted, they affirmed as **good**. Nietzsche speaks at length about these nobles, by which he means the strong, those in power in any given society, in which it was believed that the strong were good and the good were strong. He gives as an example the ancient Greek and Roman civilizations which have idolized war, strength, and masculinity.

the judgment "good" did not move here from those to whom "goodness" was shown! On the contrary, it was the "good people" themselves, that is, the noble, powerful, higher-ranking, and higher-thinking people who felt and set themselves and their actions up as good, that is to say, of the first rank, in opposition to everything low, low-minded, common, and vulgar. From this *pathos of distance* they first arrogated to themselves the right to create values, to stamp out the names for values. What did they care about usefulness! (Nietzsche: 15)

Power, strength, good, they all meant the same thing in these pre-moral times.

However, somewhere along the line, **morality got invented**: the slave revolt in morals.

The slave revolt in morality begins when the resentment itself becomes creative and gives birth to values: the resentment of those beings who are prevented from a genuine reaction, that is, something active, and who compensate for that with a merely imaginary vengeance. (Nietzsche: 24-25)

At this point, Nietzsche introduces the term "resentment." Christians and Jews during the days of the Roman Empire were an oppressed, powerless people. When they did not manage to take the worldly, material power that they desired, out of spite, they made a virtue out of their lack of control instead. They managed to cope with their powerlessness only

by convincing themselves that earthly power was not worth having, that worldly power was evil. According to Nietzsche, this is where Christian morality took root. He also claims that the development of this morality, which he calls "slave morality," (25) was a slow process, lasting about 2000 years. He also states that the chief engineers of the tenets of slave morality were the class of priests.

Further on in this study, Nietzsche claims the best example of a priestly caste harboring "ressentiment" were the Jewish priests. They managed to completely reverse former moral values, deeming the poor and wretched as good and the powerful and passionate as bad. This process of reversal, which was a slow one, eventually culminated in the advancement of Christianity. Thus, with the coming of Christianity, the reversal of moral values came to its completion. What in the past was deemed *good* became *evil*, and what once was considered *bad* became the *Christian good*.

Disdainfully, Nietzsche deems the new morality "slave morality" (25). He despises it because of its origins in hatred and denial and because "slave morality" emphasizes a promised afterlife at the expense of the self and the present. Nietzsche rejects slave morality because of its numbing effect on culture in general and on the ambition and motivation of the individual in particular.

Assuming as true what in any event is taken as "the truth" nowadays, that it is the purpose of all culture simply to breed a tame and civilized animal, a domestic pet, out of the beast of prey "man," then we would undoubtedly have to consider all those instincts of reaction and resentment with whose help the noble races and all their ideals were finally disgraced and overpowered as the essential instruments of culture—though to do that would not be to claim that the bearers of these instincts also in themselves represented culture. By contrast, the opposite would not only be probable—no! nowadays it is visibly apparent! These people carrying instincts of oppression and of a lust for revenge, the descendants of all European and non-European slavery, of all pre-Aryan populations in particular—they represent the regression of mankind! These "instruments of culture" are a disgrace to humanity, and more a reason to be suspicious of or a counterargument against "culture" in general! We may well be right when we hang onto our fear of the blond beast at the base of all noble races and keep up our guard. (Nietzsche: 30-31)

Nietzsche's "blonde beasts" are pre-slave-morality noble men, who, while respectful with their own kind, behave like uncaged beasts when leaving their own class. The word "blonde" from "blonde beasts" is a reference to

the solar nature of the noblemen and not to their hair color, as Nietzsche includes among them not only Vikings and Goths but also Arabs and Japanese noblemen.

There are several ideas that I would like to retain from Nietzsche's first essay, ideas, which in my opinion impacted Yeats's poem/ the ideas/ ideology that Yeats expresses in *The Second Coming*

1. Judeo-Christian values are not absolute values; they are the outcome of the so-called slave morality which was born out of the resentment that slaves have felt for their masters
2. The concept of the "evil enemy" is basic to "*slave morality*," just as "good" is essential to the nobleman. Therefore, what we mean by "good" nowadays is a counter-value. It is the reverse of what was thought good in the past
3. Nietzsche's fears that Christian values, the values of slave morality will bring about nihilism, the end of our civilization
4. the figure of the "blonde beast."

W. B. Yeats: *The Second Coming*

One of W.B. Yeats's most anthologized and, at the same time, most obscure poems, *The Second Coming* (1919), is, somewhat paradoxically, also one of the most often cited pieces of literature due to its heavily used or borrowed title, lines or phrases. Written in the aftermath of World War I, the poem prophesizes that some sort of Second Coming is arriving, and the anarchy in the world foreshadows it is not very far. The poem's popularity rests on the fact that it has resonated through all the cultural decays across the globe since its publication. Emblematic for its influential status is also the many later texts that paid tribute to it in various ways by using it as a source of inspiration, reiterating some of its ideas and memorable surreal imagery. The poem is divided into two stanzas, and while it contains some rhymes, it resembles a more free verse modern voice.

In the first part of the poem, the poet describes chaos as if he were an eyewitness to it. The imagery of the broken and collapsing gyres alludes to Yeats's book *A Vision* and his idea that there is something wrong with the present age, which is chaotic. Apocalyptic imagery, such as "The blood-dimmed tide is loosed" (Yeats: 294) and the metaphor "The ceremony of innocence is drowned," (Yeats 294) are Biblical allusions to the story of Noah and the flood, which drowned the wicked. The diction "Revelation" and "Second Coming" (Yeats: 294) is also biblical and very-potent poetic imagery, but, in my opinion, it is also the cause of numerous misreadings of this poem.

The biblical imagery used in this poem made scholars think that in *The Second Coming*, Yeats contrasts the civilized past, the Christian age, with the Biblical story of the Second Coming of Christ, which represents the modern age. However, in Yeats's poem, it is not Christ that is reborn, but the "rough beast" (295), which Yeats describes as "A shape with lion body and the head of a man"(294). Most critics consider the beast the sphynx of Greek mythology, a terrifying creature that tells riddles and asks unanswerable questions. The terms in which Yeats's poem describes the symbolic birth of the beast say to the reader that this is not an auspicious event. The advent of the beast marks the beginning of a new age. Most critics consider the final question a rhetorical one, and therefore a sign of Yeats's pessimistic view of the future.

I suggest a different reading for this poem: a Nietzschean one and I shall try to give some reasons why I consider that a Nietzschean reading would be appropriate.

First and foremost, Yeats was not a Christian poet; at best, he was an agnostic. In many of his writings, he questioned, just like Nietzsche, the conventional Judeo-Christian values, which he considered limiting for the individuals. Furthermore, he placed great efforts into building himself a personal religion/ philosophy. In the first two verses of *The Second Coming*, the image of the collapsing gyres allude to his book *A Vision*, which combines esoteric knowledge, philosophy, and history, and points to the fact that, despite all the biblical imagery used in it, this is not a poem that will hold up Christian values. The image of the gyres also points to the fact that this poem is about history because the gyres in Yeats's *A Vision* represent historical cycles. The questioning of Christian values and the emphasis that Yeats places on history from the beginning of the poem point towards Nietzsche's *On the Origin of Morals*.

In my opinion, *The Second Coming* is a poetic description of the collapse of a world dominated by the Nietzschean slave morality and the return of the world dominated by master morality. The terms in which the poet describes the dichotomy of good-evil are the Nietzschean terms: "The best lack all conviction" (they are weak and passive; they are the "good" of the slave morality), "while the worst/ Are full of passionate intensity." (Evil appears to be self-assured and robust) (Yeats: 294).

Then in the second half of the poem, the beast, while fierce and terrifying, is very much a solar creature, a creature of light, which has "a gaze blank and pitiless as the sun." Because of the light that it gets associated with, the beast is not evil in the conventional sense. It does not represent darkness. Furthermore, here comes the most significant misreading of the poem, the beast is described as "a shape with lion body and the head of a man" (Yeats: 294). Because of this description, many

critics think that Yeats's beast is the sphynx of Greek mythology. But they are wrong. And I shall give two reasons why they are wrong. Firstly, the Greek sphynx is described as having the head of a woman. And Yeats makes it clear that this beast has the head of a man. Secondly, the sphynx is a guardian; it guards the city of Thebes; therefore, it does not travel. So there is absolutely no reason for the sphynx of Greek mythology to go to be born in Bethlehem. It just doesn't make any sense.

The beast of Yeats's poem is the Nietzschean "blonde beast," which is a metaphor for the master: the warrior. His rebirth in Bethlehem signifies the return of master morality, the coming of an era of subjective faith. The individual finds salvation in himself and does not look for a deity outside as the objective Christian faith does.

W. H. Auden: *September 1, 1939*

September 1, 1939, is one of Wystan Hugh Auden's most famous and oft-quoted poems, a characteristic it shares with Yeats's *The Second Coming*. The poem was written in 1939, just as German troops invaded Poland at the beginning of the Second World War.

The poem is too long to be quoted at length; therefore, I will retell it in a few sentences.

At the beginning of Auden's poem, the narrator is sitting in a dive bar in New York City. Hitler's actions and the policy of appeasement following World War I have brought the 1930s, a "low dishonest decade" (86), to a close, bringing "the unmentionable odour of death" (86) to the September evening. The onset of World War II brings negative emotions: "clever hopes expire" (86). Next, the narrator contemplates Hitler's personality using a Jungian concept—a "huge imago," (86) a psychological notion of the idealized self. Finally, he envisions that historians explain how German culture, perhaps starting with Martin Luther's overhaul of Christianity hundreds of years earlier, led Germans to go along with Hitler's anti-Semitic, psychopathic evil.

Yet, says the poem's persona, it is easy to perceive the basic human patterns in the story: doing evil to someone leads that person to do evil in return. Athenian historian and general Thucydides saw how dictators abused an apathetic population to accomplish their ends in ancient Greece. Even in a 20th-century democracy like Germany (or the United States), the same pattern continues. So the story told here is not new.

In the fourth and fifth stanzas, the poet focuses on New York City, the epitome of modern capitalism, which has yielded "blind skyscrapers"

(87) that "proclaim / the strength of Collective Man" (87) through competition and heterogeneity rather than coordinated social efforts. Yet, one cost of this social blindness is isolationism. This is why people keep the music playing and the lights on so that they never see how morally lost they are. But, unfortunately, what is lacking is the perception of human selfishness that privileges the individual over the community, leading to evil and complacency and indifference when evil is happening elsewhere, as in Europe. Meanwhile, politicians: "helpless governors" (87), inevitably take advantage of these tendencies as the political "compulsory game"(87) plays out.

In the last two stanzas, the poetic voice tries to overcome the problems identified in the previous stanza: "Who can reach the deaf, / Who can speak for the dumb" (88) asks the poet.

Yet, the narrator is one of many people who provide "points of light" (89) like this poem. Contrary to the flashes of light of gunfire, the poem's arguments "flash out" as missives exchanged with other members of "the Just," those who seek justice. Although each poet writes independently, "dotted everywhere" (89) poems about solidarity and justice build a kind of solidarity. In this way, the web of poetry, the "ironical points of light," emerges spontaneously, mirroring the network of New York skyscrapers that arise without coordination and make the city.

The poet knows he is just like everyone else, "composed like them / Of Eros and dust." (89). It is a time of "negation and despair"(89) for anyone paying attention to Europe. Nevertheless, the narrator hopes his words show "an affirming flame" (89) of social awareness and care.

While Auden's poem is not a lyrical transcription of his historical ideology but was born out of the poet's concern over the commencement of World War II, it is easy to see how it continues the argument started by Yeats's *The Second Coming*. Thus, the visionary narrator of Auden's poem takes up where Yeats's detached poetic persona concluded his view and describes the commencement of a new era dominated by the beast, the new anti-Christ: Hitler. While *September 1, 1939*, like Yeats's *The Second Coming* builds on a cyclical view of history, it is not a fatalist poem, for it emphasizes social responsibility. Yet the apathy of the western world, which made Hitler's running amok possible, is a repetition of the historical pattern described in Yeats's verse: "The best lack all conviction, while the worst/ Are full of passionate intensity" (294). Thus, Auden's "dense commuters" (88), blinded by their "euphoric dream" (87) and incapable of seeing "the international wrong" (87), are instrumental in the recommencement of "the conservative dark" (88) and "the lie of Authority." (88)

Louis MacNeice: *London Rain*

Like Auden's, MacNeice's poem is a commentary on the commencement of World War II. The narrator of the poem, an avatar of the poet who used to be a fire watcher in London during World War II, observes London during a rainy night and muses over the prospects for the individual offered by the havoc caused by the war. However, while Auden's poem succumbs to the dichotomic understanding of good vs. evil, MacNeice's verse displays a more Nietzschean view of morality.

In effect, there is little difference between MacNeice's God and no-God:

Whichever wins I am happy
For God will give me bliss
But no-God will absolve me
From all I do amiss
And I need not suffer conscience
If the world was made amiss. (MacNeice)

The war, just like in Auden's poem, where it brings "waves of anger and fear" (Auden 86), leads to the individual's "wishes turn to violent/ Horses black as coal." (MacNeice) Like Yeats's "rough beast" (295). MacNeice's "stallions of the soul" bring about a new destructive world-order:

My lust goes riding horseback
To ravish where I choose,
To burgle all the turrets
Of beauty as I choose.

But unlike Yeats's *The Second Coming*, and in more consensus with Auden's *September 1, 1939*. MacNeice does not absolve the individual from political responsibility: "The world is what we make./ And we only can discover/ Life in the life we make". And yet, while assuming responsibility for the war, the visionary narrator does not give in to a pessimistic outlook but finds solace in a cyclical view of history:

There will be sunshine after
When the rain abates
And rain returning duly
When the sun abates. (MacNeice)

Conclusion

In conclusion to reading the three poems, we may state that W.H. Auden's *September 1, 1939*, and Louis MacNeice's *London Rain* are heavily indebted in content and form to Yeats's *The Second Coming*. Like Yeats's poem, the poems of Auden and MacNeice present the reader with visionary narrators that muse over the causes that bring about violent world-order changes. Like *The Second Coming*, which is heavily indebted in ideology and imagery to Friedrich Nietzsche's historical understanding of good vs. bad/evil, the poems of Auden and MacNeice focus on the dichotomy of good vs. evil, which they view more as historical constructs than fundamental concepts. All three poems feature dark and light imagery to differentiate between good and evil. In addition, all three poems display a cyclical view of history. But while Yeats's poem written in the aftermath of World War I presents the reader with a fatalistic worldview, W.H. Auden's and Louis MacNeice's World War II poems emphasize the importance of social concern and individual responsibility.

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